

1 Identification of two unannotated miRNAs in classic Hodgkin lymphoma 2 cell lines

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39 KEYWORDS

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Classic Hodgkin lymphoma (cHL), novel miRNA, loss of epigenetic control

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43 Abstract

44 MicroRNAs (miRNAs) are small non coding RNAs responsible for posttranscriptional
45 regulation of gene expression. Even though almost 2000 precursors have been described so far,
46 additional miRNAs are still being discovered in normal as well as malignant cells. Alike protein
47 coding genes, miRNAs may acquire oncogenic properties in consequence of altered expression
48 or presence of gain or loss of function mutations. In this study we mined datasets from miRNA
49 expression profiling (miRNA-seq) of 7 classic Hodgkin Lymphoma (cHL) cell lines, 10 non-Hodgkin
50 lymphoma (NHL) cell lines and 56 samples of germinal center derived B-cell lymphomas.-Our
51 aim was to discover potential novel cHL oncomiRs not reported in miRBase (release 22.1) and
52 expressed in cHL cell lines but not other B-cell lymphomas. We identified six such miRNA
53 candidates in cHL cell lines and verified the expression of two of them encoded at
54 chr2:212678788-212678849 and chr5:168090507-168090561 (GRCh38). Interestingly, we showed
55 that one of the validated miRNAs (located in an intron of the *TENM2* gene) is expressed
56 together with its host gene. *TENM2* is characterized by hypomethylation and open chromatin
57 around its TSS in cHL cell lines in contrast to NHL cell lines and germinal centre B-cells respectively.
58 It indicates an epigenetic mechanism responsible for aberrant expression of both, the *TENM2*
59 gene and the novel miRNA in cHL cell lines.

60 Despite the GO analysis performed with the input of the *in silico* predicted novel miRNA
61 target genes did not reveal ontologies typically associated with cHL pathogenesis, it pointed to
62 several interesting candidates involved in i.e. lymphopoiesis. These include the lymphoma related
63 *BCL11A* gene, the *IKZF2* gene involved in lymphocyte development or the transcription initiator
64 *GTF2H1*.

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66 Introduction

67 MicroRNAs (miRNAs) play a key role in posttranscriptional regulation of gene expression,
68 and are essential regulators of various cellular processes [1, 2]. These short RNAs incorporated
69 into the RISC complex bind to the complementary 3'UTR fragment of a target mRNA leading
70 to its degradation or inhibition of translation [3]. Aberrant miRNA expression in classic Hodgkin
71 lymphoma (cHL), a B-cell lymphoma characterized by the presence of few large neoplastic
72 Hodgkin and Reed-Sternberg (HRS) cells, was first confirmed in the early 2000s [4]. By now,
73 the role of several oncomiRs and tumor suppressor miRNAs was described in cHL [5-7]. These
74 include the deregulated miR-155 and miR-196a and miR-23a-3p, which are assumed to contribute
75 to the constitutive NFkB hyperactivation, a process crucial in cHL pathogenesis [6, 8, 9]. Moreover,
76 also other miRNAs deregulated in cHL such as miR-9, miR-138, miR-150 were described as

77 candidates involved in processes responsible for Hodgkin lymphomagenesis such as immune
78 evasion and impaired B-cell receptor signalling [9].

79 In our recent study we have performed high throughput screening of miRNA expression
80 in 7 widely used cHL cell lines and ten non-Hodgkin lymphoma cell lines (NHL) by RNA-seq [9].
81 Here we mined this dataset with the aim to find miRNAs expressed in cHL and not yet reported
82 in miRBase (release 22.1). This brought us to the identification of two molecules with typical
83 miRNA characteristics which are recurrently expressed in cHL cell lines. Moreover, our results
84 suggest that the aberrant expression of these novel miRNAs is at least to some extent caused
85 by the loss of epigenetic control in cHL cell lines.

86

87 **Materials and methods**

88 **cHL cell lines, NHL cell lines and primary cHL samples**

89 7 cHL cell lines (L-428 [10], HDLM-2 [11], KM-H2 [12], L-1236 [13], SUP-HD1 [14], U-
90 HO1 [15], L-540 [16]) and 10 NHL cell lines (Burkitt lymphoma: Raji [17], Ca46 [18], Daudi [19],
91 Namalwa [20], Ramos [21]; Diffuse Large Cell Lymphoma: OCI-LY1 [22], OCI-LY3 [22], OCI-LY7
92 [22], SU-DHL-6 [23]; B Cell Lymphoma: Val [24]) were used. Three cHL cell lines (HDLM-2, SUP-
93 HD1, U-HO1) and ten NHL cell lines (Burkitt lymphoma: Raji, Ca46, Daudi, Namalwa, Ramos;
94 Diffuse Large Cell Lymphoma: OCI-LY1, OCI-LY3, OCI-LY7, SU-DHL-6; B Cell Lymphoma: Val) were
95 obtained from DSMZ GmbH (Braunschweig, Germany). The L-428, KM-H2, L-1236, L-540 cHL cell
96 lines were obtained from collaborating partners and together with HEK-293 cell line were STR
97 typed to confirm their identity. Furthermore, the HEK-293 cell line was used for the transfection
98 experiments in functional analysis [9]. Respective cell culture conditions were described
99 previously [25].

100 Normal CD77⁺ GC (germinal centre) B cells were purified from remnants of fresh tonsils
101 of routine tonsillectomy samples using magnetic activated cell sorting (MACS; Miltenyi Biotech,
102 Bergisch Gladbach, Germany), as reported previously [26]. Primary HRS cells and negative
103 controls (empty membrane fragments adjacent to lymph node sections) were obtained by laser
104 microdissection (PALM Robot MicroBeam laser microdissection system, PALM) from HE stained
105 lymph node sections. 1000 microdissected cells were obtained from each patient and used in
106 further analyses. The local ethics committee of Goethe University Hospital (157/17) approved
107 the study and informed consent from the patients was obtained in accordance with the
108 Declaration of Helsinki. The informed consent from the patients was written and all participants
109 were adults.

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111 **Small RNA profiling (miRNA-seq)**

112 The BAM files from miRNA-seq of seven cHL cell lines and 10 NHL cell lines [9] were
113 reanalysed in order to detect unannotated RNA-like sequences as potential miRNA candidates.
114 For further identification of putative miRNAs we used the CAP-miRSeq software
115 (<http://bioinformatics.mayo.edu/research/cap-mirseq/>). miRNA candidates were compared to
116 known, annotated miRNAs from miRBase (release 22.1)[27] and selected according to structural
117 properties characteristic for miRNA sequences.

118 To identify potential miRNAs expressed in cHL we used the following criteria:

- 119 I. Not annotated miRNA expressed in at least 3/7 of the analyzed cHL cell lines and
120 absent in NHL cell lines ("expressed" defined as mean \geq 20 CPM (Counts Per Million)
121 in cell lines with expression).
- 122 II. Not annotated miRNAs expressed in less than 2% of the analyzed samples from
123 previously published miRnome sequencing data including 56 primary germinal center
124 derived B-cell lymphomas (16 Burkitt lymphomas, 19 diffuse large B-cell lymphomas,
125 and 21 follicular lymphomas recently analysed within the International Cancer Genome
126 Consortium Project "Determining Molecular Mechanisms in Malignant Lymphoma by
127 Sequencing" (ICGC MMML-Seq)[28]
- 128 III. Manual curation in order to exclude known miRNAs, palindromic sequences, artefacts
129 and other small ncRNAs.

130 *RNA isolation and real-time qPCR analyses*

131 cDNA templates for RT-qPCR we obtained by reverse transcription of 10 ng of total RNA
132 (cHL cell lines and germinal center B-cells - GCB) and 10 μ l of miRNA containing eluate (HRS
133 cells obtained as described by Küppers et al. [29]) using TaqMan™ Advanced miRNA cDNA
134 Synthesis Kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific) [30] according to manufacturer's protocol. Real-time qPCR
135 was performed using custom TaqMan™ probes corresponding to the mature miRNA sequence
136 for each of the selected candidate miRNA (**S1 Table**). Relative expression of selected miRNAs
137 was calculated using BioRad Genex software [31] in relation to reference miRNAs (miR-191-5p
138 and miR-361-5) as described previously [25].

139 For mRNA expression analysis total RNA (500 ng) isolated from the cell lines using Trizol
140 [32] was reverse transcribed using Maxima First Strand cDNA Synthesis Kit (Thermo Scientific,
141 USA) as described in the manufacturer's protocol. Primers were designed using Primer 3 Plus
142 software (**S2 Table**). PCR reactions were performed as described previously [33]. The results
143 were analysed using BioRad Genex software in respect to the *ACTB* and *GAPDH* reference
144 genes. The BioRad Genex software determines particular cycles (Ct) using automatically generated

145 background values. Next, for each sample, it calculates the quantity relative to control genes, taking
146 into account the amplification efficiency of qPCR for each gene [31].

147 **miRNA gene cloning and transfection**

148 Selected novel miRNA genes were amplified with 100 bp flanks using primers designed
149 with the Primer 3 Plus software (**S3 Table**). PCR products were cloned into the pCDH-CMV-MCS-
150 EF1 α -Green Puro cloning vector (SBI, Palo Alto, CA, USA) and used for transformation of JM109
151 *E.coli* competent cells (Promega) as described previously [34]. The plasmid DNA (pDNA) was
152 isolated using PhasePrepTM BAC DNA kit (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA). For transfection of
153 the HEK-293 cell line the Lipofectamine RNAiMAX Transfection Reagent (Invitrogen, Karlsruhe,
154 Germany) was used according to the manufacturer's protocol. For control purposes the same
155 cell line was transfected using the empty vector. Each transfection was performed in two
156 biological replicates. Two days past transfection, total RNA was isolated using Trizol. Reverse
157 transcription and real-time qPCR reactions were performed as described above. The transfection
158 efficiency of HEK-293 cells was measured using JuLi Br & FL Station (NanoEnTek, Seoul, Korea)
159 by the calculation of GFP positive cells. RT-qPCR miRNA expression from the construct was
160 measured using same TaqManTM probes as described above in reference to hsa-miR-423-3p
161 (**Table S1**) [25].

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163 **DNA isolation and bisulfite DNA pyrosequencing**

164 DNA from cell lines was isolated using phenol/chloroform and Phase Lock GelTM tubes
165 (5Prime Quantabio, Beverly, MA, USA) followed by ethanol precipitation and used for bisulfite
166 conversion.

167 DNA was bisulfite converted using the EpiTect DNA Modification Kit (Qiagen, Hilden,
168 Germany) according to the manufacturer's protocol. PCR reactions were prepared using PyroMark
169 PCR Kit (Qiagen) in a DNA/RNA UV-cleaner box UVC/T-AR (Biosan, Riga, Latvia). The PCR reaction
170 mixture contained: 12.5 μ l PyroMark Master Mix; 0.5 μ l (20 pmol/ μ l) of F and R primer, 2.4
171 μ l CoralLoad, 1 μ l of converted DNA (~25 ng/ μ l) and 8 μ l of RNase-Free water. PCR primers
172 (assays) (**S4 Table**) designed using the PyroMark Assay Design 2.0 software (Qiagen, Germany)
173 were used for DNA methylation analysis of three regions corresponding to the two novel miRNA
174 candidates:

175 1. 2_nv_chr2_212678788 novel miRNA candidate:

- 176 • region (I) located 54 bp upstream of the miRNA gene, amplified sequence:
177 chr2:212,678,797-212,679,018 (GRCh38/hg38), genomic position of analysed
178 dinucleotides: chr2:212,678,922; chr2:212,678,938; chr2:212,678,945 (GRCh38/hg38).

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180 2. 3_nv_chr5_168090507 novel miRNA candidate:

- 181 • Region (I) 166 bp upstream of *TENM2* (transcript uc010jld.3, putative novel miRNA
182 primary transcript, amplified sequence: chr5:167,284,564-167,284,717 (GRCh38/hg38),
183 the genomic position of analysed dinucleotide: chr5:167,284,682 (GRCh38/hg38),
- 184 • Region (II); ~2 kb upstream of the miRNA gene, amplified sequence:
185 chr5:168,088,403-168,088,609 (GRCh38/hg38), genomic position of analysed
186 dinucleotides: chr5:168,088,484; chr5:168,088,488; chr5:168,088,497;
187 chr5:168,088,504; chr5:168,088,522; chr5:168,088,531; chr5:168,088,535
188 (GRCh38/hg38).

189 PCR reactions were performed in the following conditions: 95°C for 15 min × 1; 94°C for 30 s,
190 59°C for 30 s, 72°C for 30 s × 45; 72°C for 10 min × 1; 4°C ∞. The products were visualised
191 on 1.8% agarose gel with SimplySafe™ (EURx) under UV light (BioDoc-it Imaging System, UVP,
192 USA). Purification of PCR products and pyrosequencing was performed as described previously
193 [35]. Each pyrosequencing experiment was performed with fully methylated DNA control (CpG
194 Genome Universal Millipore, Darmstadt, Germany) and unmethylated whole genome amplified
195 (WGA) control obtained using GenomePlex® Whole Genome Amplification Kit (Sigma-Aldrich,
196 Steinheim, Germany).

197 **Histone mark H3K27ac ChIP-seq (Chromatin immunoprecipitation-** 198 **sequencing)**

199 Cross-linking of cHL cells (7 cHL cell lines) and 3 germinal center B-cell pools (GCBs),
200 (~10⁶ cells per cell line, cHL and GCB respectively) was performed by incubating the cells
201 in 1% formaldehyde for 8 minutes in RT. Thereafter, genomic DNA was sonicated using Covaris™
202 E220 device in order to obtain 50-500 bp length DNA fragments. Chromatin preparation and
203 histone ChIP were performed according to the BLUEPRINT protocols ([https://www.blueprint-
204 epigenome.eu/index.cfm?p=7BF8A4B6-F4FE-861A-2AD57A08D63D0B58](https://www.blueprint-epigenome.eu/index.cfm?p=7BF8A4B6-F4FE-861A-2AD57A08D63D0B58)) using the anti-H3K27ac
205 (Diagenode C15410196, lot no. A1723-0041D) antibody. The library for high-throughput
206 sequencing was prepared using Kapa Hyper Prep Kit (Kapa Biosystems, Roche, Basel, Switzerland)
207 according to the BLUEPRINT protocol. Briefly, end repair and A-Tailing was followed by adapter
208 ligation. Library amplification was performed in the following conditions 98°C for 45 s x1; 98°C
209 for 15 s, 60°C for 30 s, 72°C for 30 s x 12; 72°C for 1 min; 12°C ∞. PCR products were
210 cleaned using AMPure XP beads followed by size selection of DNA fragments (300 bp) with E-
211 Gel™ SizeSelect™ (Invitrogen, Waltham, Massachusetts, USA).

212 High-throughput sequencing was carried out using the HiSeq2500 (Illumina) sequencer
213 [36]. Raw reads (fastq) were mapped to the GRCh38 reference genome using BWA aligner (aln,
214 samse) [37]. Obtained bam files were sorted (Samtools) and peaks were called using MACS2
215 [38, 39]. DESeq2 R package was used in order to determine the active and inactive chromatin
216 regions in cHL compared to GCB controls [40].

217 ***In silico* functional enrichment analysis of novel miRNA target** 218 **genes**

219 In order to identify potential gene targets for the novel experimentally confirmed miRNAs
220 two freely available tools were used: miRDB [41] and miRanda [42] allowing for custom target
221 prediction. The complete set of human genes (3'UTRs) was used as the reference. This analyses
222 resulted in two cohorts of potential targets for each of the novel miRNAs. We further selected
223 potential target genes according to the following criteria:

- 224 • total score > 280 for miRanda and > 80 for miRDB,
- 225 • only genes present in both cohorts for each of the analysed novel miRNA
226 respectively.

227 These gene sets were used as the input for Gene Ontology (GO) analyses performed using
228 STRING [43] and GO Consortium database [44, 45]. Finally, we selected the common set of
229 biological processes returned from both tools.

230 **Further validation of novel miRNA candidates**

231 For additional validation of novel miRNA candidates, cDNA templates and RT-qPCR products
232 were obtained using Custom TaqMan™ Small RNA Assay (Thermo Fisher Scientific) with the same
233 custom miRNA probes as described above (**Table S1**). The RT-qPCR products were visualized on 1.8%
234 agarose gel with SimplySafe™ (EURx) under UV light (BioDoc-it Imaging System, UVP, USA) and
235 purified using DNA Clean & Concentrator–5 Kit (Zymo Research, Germany). PCR products were
236 subjected to A-tailing procedure (30 minutes, 70 °C) followed by ligation reaction with pGEM®-T Easy
237 Vector (Promega; 16 hours in 4 °C). Obtained constructs were used for transformation of JM109 *E.coli*
238 competent cells (Promega). Lastly, colony PCR was performed using M13 primers (**S5 Table**) according
239 to the following protocol: 95 °C for 2 min × 1; (95 °C for 30 s, 55 °C for 30 s, 72 °C for 30 s) × 30, 72 °C
240 for 5 min × 1. Obtained PCR products were then visualised, purified and sequenced (Sanger) as
241 described previously. [25]

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260 The second novel molecule (3_nv_chr5_168090507) was confirmed to be expressed by
 261 RT-qPCR in 2 of 3 cHL cell lines (SUP-HD1, HDLM-2 but not KM-H2) indicated initially by the
 262 NGS experiment (**Fig 2B**). In summary, these analyses allowed the identification of two novel
 263 miRNAs recurrently expressed in cHL cell lines.

Figure II

A. 2_nv_chr2_212678788

B.

Fig 2. The comparison of log10 normalized relative expression of validated miRNAs. Black bars represent NGS experiment (CPM) and white bars the RT-qPCR relative expression. The RT-qPCR detection thresholds

were obtained by adding the standard deviation of the RT-qPCR results to the mean relative expression level for each miRNA, respectively.

264 **Validation of 2_nv_chr2_212678788 and 3_nv_chr5_168090507** 265 **miRNA expression in cHL cell lines**

266 We next performed an additional validation step of the two unannotated miRNAs
267 (nv_chr2_212678788 and 3_nv_chr5_168090507). We used an alternative reverse transcription kit
268 which allows individual amplification of the miRNAs of interest followed by qPCR with the same
269 custom probes as used previously.

270 Importantly, we observed expression of particular unannotated miRNAs in the same cHL
271 cell lines as indicated by both NGS and previous RT-qPCR experiments (alternative approach).
272 Lastly, we cloned the obtained PCR products and performed Sanger sequencing. It showed the
273 presence of particular unannotated miRNA sequences (mature miRNA molecules of
274 nv_chr2_212678788 and 3_nv_chr5_168090507) in the respective cHL cell lines (**S6 Table**).

275 **2_nv_chr2_212678788 and 3_nv_chr5_168090507 precursors** 276 **undergo physiological processing yielding mature miRNAs**

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278 To analyze if 2_nv_chr2_212678788 and 3_nv_chr5_168090507 undergo canonical miRNA
279 biogenesis we cloned the PCR products containing the entire miRNA precursor sequences into
280 the pCDH-CMV-MCS-EF1 α -Green Puro cloning vector and used these constructs to transfect the
281 HEK-293 cell line. We recurrently observed the expression of both novel miRNAs after
282 transfection with the miRNA constructs, whereas no expression of the novel miRNAs was
283 observed in samples transfected with the empty vector (**Fig 3**). In summary, these results
284 demonstrate that 2_nv_chr2_212678788 and 3_nv_chr5_168090507 precursors are processed by
285 the cell into mature miRNAs identified using the TaqManTM assays.

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Figure III

Fig 3. Expression of novel miRNAs in transfected HEK-293 cell line. RT-qPCR amplification curves showing expression of the mature sequences of novel miRNAs in the HEK-293 cell line transfected with the constructs containing the novel miRNA genes (upper panel) and empty vector (lower panel) respectively. Green curves represent expression of mature novel miRNAs **A:** of 2_nv_chr2_212678788 and **B:** of 3_nv_chr5_168090507. Red curves represent the expression of the reference hsa-miR-423-3p.

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288 **DNA hypomethylation and chromatin activation drives** 289 **expression of the novel miRNA 3_nv_chr5_168090507**

290 As HRS cells are characterised by global epigenetic reprogramming which includes
291 alteration of DNA methylation of promoter regions and loss of epigenetic control of LTRs. We
292 hypothesized that the expression of the two novel miRNAs 3_nv_chr5_168090507 and
293 2_nv_chr2_212678788 is triggered by specific DNA hypomethylation in the analyzed cell lines.
294 In order to test this hypothesis three pyrosequencing assays were designed to analyze for
295 potential hypomethylation in the respective regions. DNA methylation levels in cHL cell lines
296 were compared to NHL cell lines that do not express these novel miRNAs. Because of the
297 intronic localization of the 3_nv_chr5_168090507 miRNA gene, it can be transcribed canonically,
298 as a separate miRNA gene, or non-canonically together with the large *TENM2* transcript
299 (uc010jdd.3 – largest gene transcript with the highest level of review) as a mirtron [46].
300 Therefore, for this novel miRNA, two pyrosequencing assays were designed to test both
301 possibilities. The first in the vicinity of the miRNA (~2 kb upstream, putative miRNA gene,
302 *TENM2* intronic sequence) and the second region 166 bp upstream of the *TENM2* gene TSS
303 (**Fig 4**). The second analyzed miRNA (2_nv_chr2_212678788) is located in a gene desert, in a
304 THE1C LTR, therefore only the region within the LTR and adjacent to the miRNA was tested
305 (54 bp upstream).

Figure IV

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Fig 4. Visualisation of the genomic positions (GRCh38) of bisulfite pyrosequencing assays used for DNA methylation analysis of the novel 3_nv_chr5_168090507 miRNA. Two regions were examined (blue). Region (I) 166 bp upstream of TSS of *TENM2* (A) and region (II) adjacent (~2 kb upstream) to novel miRNA gene (*TENM2* intron) (B).

The mean methylation level in the vicinity of the 3_nv_chr5_168090507 miRNA gene (assay II; 7 CG dinucleotides) was 79% (range: 1-100; sd=24) in the cHL cell lines and 82% (range: 2-97%; sd=17) in the NHL cell lines showing no significant difference in DNA methylation level between the studied lymphoma types. Similarly, no differences were observed for the LTR located 2_nv_chr2_212678788 miRNA for which the mean methylation level (3 CG dinucleotides) was 76% (range: 5-99%; sd=28) in the cHL cell lines and 75% (range: 24-99%; sd=19) in the NHL cell lines. This finding suggests that activation 2_nv_chr2_212678788 miRNA is not a direct effect of the respective LTR hypomethylation. However, we observed significant hypomethylation ($p < 0.05$) of the *TENM2* promoter region (host gene of 3_nv_chr5_168090507 miRNA) using assay I; 1 CG dinucleotide (Fig 5A and 5B) in cHL cell lines (mean methylation level 9%: range: 3-15%; sd=5) compared to NHL cell lines (mean methylation level: 57.5% range: 13-77%; sd=21). Summarizing, DNA hypomethylation of the *TENM2* promoter region is a potential mechanism responsible for 3_nv_chr5_168090507 transcriptional activation in cHL.

Moreover, to test if hypomethylation observed in the *TENM2* promoter region indeed results in elevated expression of the gene (3_nv_chr5_168090507 primary transcript) we performed RT-qPCR to quantify *TENM2* expression. It indicated a negative correlation ($R < -0.5$, $p < 0.05$) (Fig 5C) between the level of expression and DNA methylation of *TENM2* promoter region. These data suggest that *TENM2* is epigenetically regulated in cHL and NHL cell lines. The expression of miRNA 3_nv_chr5_168090507 in the KM-H2, SUP-HD-1, and HDLM-2 cell lines, which also showed the highest *TENM2* expression, renders it likely that this novel miRNA is transcribed together with the *TENM2* host-gene.

In order to further confirm this mechanism we studied ChIP-seq data (H3K27ac) of the 7 cHL cell lines, 3 GCB cell pools (controls) and 5 NHL cell lines (controls, external data). We focused

335 on the *TENM2* promoter region to look for changes in the chromatin activity. The experiment
 336 showed open chromatin regions near proximal *TENM2* TSS the cHL cell lines compared to fully
 337 closed chromatin in the GCB cell controls (Fig 6) and the studied NHL cell lines: BL2, DG-75, KARPAS-
 338 422, SU-DHL-5, Z-138 (S1 Fig). The highest chromatin activity was observed in KM-H2, SUP-HD-1
 339 and HDLM-2 cell lines (Fig 6) what translates into elevated relative expression of *TENM2* and
 340 the novel miRNA in these cHL cell lines (Fig 5B).

Figure V

Fig 5. Comparison of DNA methylation level of the *TENM2* promoter region with relative expression of this gene. Bars represent methylation of one CG dinucleotide analysed by the bisulfite pyrosequencing assay (A) and *TENM2* relative expression (B). Statistically significant negative correlation

between *TENM2* relative expression and DNA methylation in cHL (black dots) and NHL cell lines (grey dots) (C).

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Figure VI

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Fig 6. *TENM2* ChIP-seq results in cHL cell lines and GCBs. The visualisation (IGV)[47] of ChIP-seq (H3K27ac) experiment performed on 7 cHL cell lines and 3 GCB cell pools (left panel). The 27th lysine acetylation for *TENM2* promoter region shows higher chromatin activity in KM-H2, SUP-HD1 and HDLM-2 cHL cell lines (blue peaks). Grey peaks represent cHL cell lines with less activated chromatin, whereas chromatin is closed in the GCB controls (green peaks).

349 **Expression of novel miRNA 3_nv_chr5_168090507 in primary** 350 **microdissected HRS cells**

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In order to test if overexpression of the novel 3_nv_chr5_168090507 miRNA is only due to the deregulation of cHL cell lines or is also found in primary cHL cases, we next analysed its expression in 10 primary microdissected HRS cell pools. No expression of the novel miRNA 3_nv_chr5_168090507 was observed in the HRS cells (S2 Fig), what in part may be caused by the low performance of the TaqMan probe in the microdissected samples. Therefore, the novel miRNA 3_nv_chr5_168090507 is expressed only in the analysed cHL cell lines or its expression level in the microdissected HRS cells is beyond the detection level of the used technique.

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358 **The novel 2_nv_chr2_212678788 is localized in long tandem repeat** 359 **region**

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It has recently shown, that aberrant activation of more than 1800 LTRs in cHL participates in global transcriptional deregulation of protein coding genes in this lymphoma [48]. Moreover, we have previously shown that this phenomenon leads to a cHL specific expression of the oncogene *CSF1R* that is crucial for the survival of HRS cells [49]. In light of these findings we

364 found it particularly interesting that the novel miRNA 2_nv_chr2_212678788 is localized within
 365 a LTR THE1C from ERVL-MaLR family (**Fig 7**) that triggers the tempting speculation that its
 366 aberrant expression may be driven by the LTR's transcriptional re-activation [49]. We therefore
 367 mined the RACE-seq data published by Edginton-White et al. but found no transcriptional activity
 368 reported within this region [48]. This finding is consistent with our ChIP-seq data (H3K27ac)
 369 which showed closed chromatin in this region in all 7 cHL cell lines as well as 3 GCB cell pools
 370 used as controls. In conclusion, the mechanism which drives the observed expression of miRNA
 371 2_nv_chr2_212678788 is probably not related to aberrant activation of LTRs in cHL.

Figure VII

372 **Fig 7. Visualisation of 2_nv_chr2_212678788 novel miRNA genomic position.** Genomic position (GRCh38) of
 novel miRNA 2_nv_chr2_212678788 sequence located in THE1C LTR.

373

374 **The novel 2_nv_chr2_212678788 miRNA is involved in various**
 375 **regulatory processes**

376 Based on the criteria outlined in the methods section, custom miRNA target prediction
 377 for the novel miRNAs resulted in 45 genes (miRDB (<http://mirdb.org/>), miRanda
 378 (<http://cbio.mskcc.org/miRNA2003/miranda.html>)) for 2_nv_chr2_212678788 and 9 genes for
 379 3_nv_chr5_168090507 indicated by both tools. The GO analysis performed using obtained cohorts
 380 of genes, resulted in 13 biological processes for 2_nv_chr2_212678788 (indicated independently
 381 by both tools, STRING, GO Consortium; FDR < 0.05) (**S7 Table**) and no biological process for
 382 3_nv_chr5_168090507. For 2_nv_chr2_212678788 these included several processes responsible
 383 for regulation of gene expression, metabolic processes and circadian regulation. Although, these
 384 processes are generally related to malignant transformation, no ontologies typically associated
 385 with cHL pathogenesis were identified.

386

387 **Discussion**

388 MicroRNAs are important factors involved in post-transcriptional regulation of gene
389 expression. These molecules were also shown to play a substantial role in various processes
390 related to lymphocyte proliferation and differentiation [50].

391 We and other groups have recently performed high throughput experiments to
392 characterize the miRnome of cHL cell lines [9, 51, 52]. In the present study we reanalysed this
393 dataset and identified 6 promising novel miRNA candidates expressed exclusively in cHL cell
394 lines. Two of them were successfully confirmed using RT-qPCR with custom TaqMan™ probes
395 and downstream analyses. However, both validated miRNAs as well as the other four candidates
396 were characterized by low relative expression (CPM below 100). It may potentially explain why
397 only two of the six novel miRNAs were confirmed experimentally. Alternatively, despite of
398 accurate filtering of false positive results, these four unconfirmed miRNAs may be in fact low
399 expressed artifacts wrongly annotated as miRNAs.

400 By cloning and transfecting the precursor sequences of the two novel miRNAs
401 (2_nv_chr2_212678788 and 3_nv_chr5_168090507) to the HEK-293 cell line and downstream
402 detection of the mature sequences we demonstrated that both miRNAs are biologically processed
403 by the cell. Therefore, these two yet unannotated miRNAs are potentially functional. However,
404 their low expression level leaves doubts on their physiological relevance in cHL. In addition, the
405 qRT-PCR experiments on microdissected HRS cells did not confirm the presence of these miRNAs
406 in the primary cells. This may be on one hand due to technical reasons investigating a small
407 number of the analyzed, pooled, microdissected cells (1000) which in combination with the low
408 expression of these miRNAs may be below the detection level of the technique. On the other
409 hand, this may also indicate that their low expression is a side effect of the global transcriptional
410 reprogramming of the studied cHL cell lines or it may be indicative for therapy-refractory
411 disease. In line with this assumption we observed DNA hypomethylation of *TENM2* gene (region
412 <200 bp upstream of TSS) harboring the 3_nv_chr5_168090507 miRNA, in cHL cell lines
413 compared to NHL cell lines. Moreover, we noticed the expression of *TENM2* (uc010jld.3
414 transcript) exclusively in the KM-H2, SUP-HD-1 and HDLM-2 cell lines that correlates to elevated
415 chromatin activity (H3K27ac ChIP-seq) around the *TENM2* TSS in these cell lines. Thus, our
416 results indicate that DNA hypomethylation is the mechanism responsible for transcriptional
417 activation of both, the *TENM2* gene itself and the 3_nv_chr5_168090507 miRNA in cHL cell
418 lines. Noteworthy, the *TENM2* gene was not reported to be associated with cHL pathogenesis
419 itself.

420 In contrast to 3_nv_chr5_168090507 miRNA we did not identify the mechanism behind the
421 activation of miRNA 2_nv_chr2_212678788 .

422

423 Finally, we performed *in silico* GO analysis using the 45 (2_nv_chr2_212678788) and 9
 424 (3_nv_chr5_168090507) target genes of these miRNAs as input. The analysis indicated an
 425 enrichment by terms related to metabolism and regulation of gene expression. How far these
 426 processes reflect malignant transformation in cHL remains to be studied.

427

428 Conclusions

429 In this study we discovered two unannotated miRNAs expressed exclusively in cHL cell
 430 lines. Using a functional approach, we proved that the molecules undergo a typical processing
 431 for miRNAs resulting in the expression of mature miRNA sequences. Moreover, we identified
 432 DNA hypomethylation and chromatin activity as mechanism for the transcriptional activation of
 433 3_nv_chr5_168090507 miRNA in cHL cell lines.

434 **Table I.** Characterization of novel miRNA candidates. Expression of the bolded candidates was confirmed
 435 using RT-qPCR with TaqMan™ probes.

Chr	Start (GRCh38)	Stop (GRCh38)	Novel miRNA candidate ID	Expressed in cHL cell lines (NGS)	Mean CPM	Expressed in non-HL cases	Validation in cHL cell lines (RT-qPCR)
chr2	212678788	212678849	2_nv_chr2_212678788	L-428, L-1236, U-HO1, SUP-HD1	23	0/56 (0%)	Confirmed in 4/4 cell lines
chr5	168090507	168090561	3_nv_chr5_168090507	KM-H2, SUP-HD1, HDLM-2	40	1/56 (1.7%)	Confirmed in 2/3 cell lines
chr6	1475207	1475275	1_nv_chr6_1475207	L-428, U-HO1, HDLM-2	74	0/56 (0%)	Not confirmed
chr6	149118294	149118354	6_nv_chr6_149118294	L-428, L540, HDLM-2	35	0/56 (0%)	Not confirmed
chr7	9978163	9978226	7_nv_chr7_9978163	L-428, U-HO1, SUP-HD1	22	0/56 (0%)	Not confirmed
chr19	6613612	6613674	4_nv_chr19_6613612	L-428, L-540, SUP-HD1	27	0/56 (0%)	Not confirmed

436

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441

442 **Competing Interests statement**

443 The authors declare no competing interests.

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451 **Author contributions**

452 AU, MG – prepared the manuscript; AU, SB, VC – performed bioinformatic analysis; AU,
453 JP, JB, JJ, NR – performed experiments, analyzed data; SH, MLH – characterized and provided
454 biological material; MG - designed the study, supervised the research and analyzed data; RS,
455 JMS – proofread the manuscript, analyzed and interpreted data. All authors read and approved
456 the manuscript.

457

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